

Oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate in aqueous perchloric acid medium – A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate has been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous perchloric acid medium. The stoichiometry is 2 : 3 i.e., two moles of quinolinium dichromate requires three moles of ethylene glycol. The reaction is first order with respect to quinolinium dichromate and ethylene glycol concentrations. Increase in perchloric acid concentration increases the reaction rate. The order with respect to acid concentration is nearly two. Added products do not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction. Increasing ionic strength and decreasing dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. A possible mechanism is proposed and reaction constants involved have been determined. The activation parameters were determined with respect to slow step of mechanism.

Keywords : Perchloric acid, ethylene glycol, quinolinium dichromate, oxidation.

Introduction

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of chromium(VI) has been well studied, chromic acid being one of the most versatile available oxidizing agents, reacting with diverse substrates. Nowadays the development of newer chromium(VI) reagents¹⁻⁶ for the oxidation of organic substrates continues to be of interest. Among the reagents employed for these investigations, quinolinium dichromate (QDC), $(C_9H_7NH^+)_2Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ is a useful and versatile oxidant that deserves further evaluation. The reduction potential of the couple i.e. Cr^{VI}/Cr^{III} is 1.33 V in acid solutions⁷. Ethylene glycol (1,2-diol) is mainly used as preservative, coolant, hydrate inhibition etc. Ethylene glycol has become increasingly important in plastic industry for the manufacture of polyester fibers and resins including polyethylene terephthalate. Ethylene glycol has been oxidized by different oxidants to give different products⁸. In literature some kinetic studies of oxidation of inorganic substrates by quinolinium dichromate (QDC) are available⁹. We are particularly interested to see the mechanism involved in the oxidation of organic substrates by quinolinium dichromate (QDC). Since chromium exhibits different oxidation states during the oxidation, such as chromium(V), chromium(IV), chromium(III) etc., the reaction might involve several complexities. There are no reports on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate. Hence we have

undertaken the oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate in perchloric acid medium to understand the behavior of active species of oxidant and reductant in such medium and to explore a suitable mechanism.

Results and discussion

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

Different sets of concentrations of reactants in 1.0 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid and at constant ionic strength, $I = 1.10$ mol dm^{-3} were kept for over 6 h at 25 °C in a closed container. When $[QDC] > [ethylene\ glycol]$ the remaining QDC was assayed by measuring the absorbance at 440 nm. The concentration of chromium(III) was determined by measuring the absorbance at 580 nm. The reaction product was identified as glycollic aldehyde by spot test¹⁰, TLC and by IR spectrum, which showed the band at 1740 cm^{-1} for C=O and -OH stretching at 3419 cm^{-1} . The results indicate that two moles of quinolinium dichromate reacts with three moles of ethylene glycol as given in eq. (1).

The reaction orders were determined from the slopes of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \log (concentration) plots or k_{obs} versus [reactant] plots by varying the concentrations of the reductant, acid etc., in turn while keeping the others constant.

The quinolinium dichromate (QDC) concentration was varied in the range of 0.5×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-3} mol

At constant concentrations of oxidant, reductant and at constant ionic strength, as the perchloric acid concentration increased, the rate of reaction also increased (Table 1). The order with respect to acid concentration, from the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{HClO}_4]$, was found to be nearly two (1.83), in the 0.10 – 1.0 mol dm^{-3} concentration range of perchloric acid (Fig. 2). A plot of k_{obs} /

Table 1. Effect of variation of QDC, ethylene glycol and perchloric acid concentrations on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by QDC at 25 °C and $I = 1.10$ mol dm^{-3}

[QDC] $\times 10^3$ (mol dm^{-3})	[Ethylene glycol] $\times 10^2$ (mol dm^{-3})	[HClO ₄] (mol dm^{-3})	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_{\text{calcd}} \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{Ethylene glycol}]$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
0.5	5.0	1.0	2.86	2.75	-
1.0	5.0	1.0	2.88	2.75	-
2.0	5.0	1.0	2.86	2.75	-
3.0	5.0	1.0	2.89	2.75	-
4.0	5.0	1.0	2.83	2.75	-
5.0	5.0	1.0	2.83	2.75	-
1.0	0.5	1.0	0.26	0.26	5.2
1.0	1.0	1.0	0.52	0.53	5.2
1.0	2.0	1.0	1.06	1.07	5.3
1.0	3.0	1.0	1.59	1.61	5.3
1.0	4.0	1.0	2.14	2.15	5.3
1.0	5.0	1.0	2.88	2.75	5.2
1.0	5.0	0.1	0.04	0.04	-
1.0	5.0	0.2	0.25	0.25	-
1.0	5.0	0.3	0.41	0.41	-
1.0	5.0	0.5	1.00	1.02	-
1.0	5.0	0.7	1.70	1.71	-
1.0	5.0	0.9	2.50	2.38	-
1.0	5.0	1.0	2.88	2.75	-

dm^{-3} with known concentration of ethylene glycol, perchloric acid and at constant ionic strength, $I = 1.10$ mol dm^{-3} (Table 1). The plot of \log (absorbance) versus time were linear over three half lives of reaction for different initial QDC concentration (Fig. 1), which indicates the unit order with respect to QDC concentration. This was confirmed by the almost constant values of rate constant k_{obs} for different QDC concentration (Table 1). The substrate ethylene glycol concentration was varied in the concentration range 0.50×10^{-2} to 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} at 25 °C keeping all other reactant concentration and conditions constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , increased with increase in the concentration of ethylene glycol (Table 1). The order with respect to ethylene glycol concentration was found to be unity.

Fig. 1. First order plots of oxidation of ethylene glycol by QDC in acid medium at 25 °C : [Ethylene glycol] = 5.0×10^{-2} ; [HClO₄] = 1.0; $I = 1.10$ mol dm^{-3} . [QDC] $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} : (1) 0.5, (2) 1.0, (3) 2.0, (4) 3.0, (5) 4.0, (6) 5.0.

$[\text{HClO}_4]$ versus $[\text{HClO}_4]$ is linear with a very small intercept and the slope being nearly ten times greater than the intercept (Fig. 2). Thus the reaction involving two protons, either as the monoprotonated oxidant species or diprotonated oxidant species is likely to be the dominant path.

Fig. 2. Order with respect to HClO_4 concentration and the plot of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{HClO}_4]$ versus $[\text{HClO}_4]$ (Conditions as in Table 1).

The effect of initially added products, chromium(III), and glycollic aldehyde was studied in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-4} to 5.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} by keeping the reactant concentrations and all other conditions constant. It was observed that, the added products do not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

When the acetic acid content (v/v) in the reaction medium was increased i.e. when the dielectric constant (D) of the medium decreased, keeping the reactants and other conditions constant, the pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} also increases. Since the dielectric constants of aqueous ethanoic acid are not available in the literature, they were computed from the values of pure liquids¹¹. No appreciable reaction of the solvent with the oxidant occurred under the experimental conditions employed. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/D$ is linear with positive slope (Fig. 3). Variation of ionic strength between 1.10 and 3.0 mol dm^{-3} using sodium perchlorate caused an increase in the rate of reaction. A plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus \sqrt{I} is also linear with positive slope (Fig. 3).

At constant concentrations of reactants and with other conditions constant, ions such as Cu^{2+} , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- did not have any significant effect on the rate of reaction, where as added Mn^{2+} decreases the rate.

Fig. 3. Effect of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the medium on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate at 25 °C.

The interaction of free radicals was examined as follows : The reaction mixture, to which a known quantity of acrylonitrile scavenger has been added initially, was kept for 3 h in an inert atmosphere. Upon diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, a white precipitate resulted indicating the participation of free radicals in the reaction.

The rate of reaction was measured at four different temperatures, 20, 25, 30 and 35 °C by varying perchloric acid concentration. The rate of reaction increased with increase in temperature. The rate constants (k) of the slow step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercepts of [ethylene glycol]/ k_{obs} versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ plots at 20, 25, 30, and 35 °C. The energy of activation for rate determining step was obtained from a plot of $\log k$ versus $1/T$, from which activation parameters were calculated. The values are given in Table 2. Thermodynamic quantities of first step of Scheme 1 were evaluated from the slope of the plot of [ethylene glycol]/ k_{obs} versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ at different temperatures (Table 2). van't Hoff plot was drawn for the variation of K with temperature ($\log K$ versus $1/T$). The values of thermodynamic quantities are given in Table 2. A comparison of these values with those values obtained for the slow step shows that the reaction before the rate-determining step is fairly rapid.

The stoichiometry of the reaction of QDC with ethylene glycol was found to be 2 : 3. Variations of concentrations of each of the oxidant (QDC), substrate (ethylene glycol) and acid (perchloric acid), while keeping all other conditions constant, showed that reaction exhibits first

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate in perchloric acid, $I = 1.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Activation parameters with respect to slow step of Scheme 1 :		
Temp. (K)	$10^2 k \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$	Activation parameters
293	0.51	$E_a = 81 \pm 3 \text{ kJ/mol}$
298	1.18	$\Delta H^\ddagger = 78 \pm 3 \text{ kJ/mol}$
303	1.56	$\Delta S^\ddagger = -19 \pm 4 \text{ JK/mol}$
308	2.79	$\Delta G^\ddagger = 84 \pm 2 \text{ kJ/mol}$
		$\log A = 12 \pm 0.5$
Thermodynamic quantities with respect to first step of Scheme 1 :		
Temp. (K)	$K \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{)}$	Thermodynamic quantities
293	0.71	$\Delta H = 15.0$
298	0.83	$\Delta S = 47.0$
303	0.88	$\Delta G = 0.41$
308	0.97	

order with respect to oxidant and substrate concentration and nearly of the order of two with respect to acid concentration. These experimental results can be accommodated in the form of following mechanism (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In a pre-equilibrium step, QDC reacts with two moles of acid to give H_2CrO_4 species, which is in accordance with the observed order of two in acid concentration. It is a well known fact that in aqueous acid solutions chromium(VI) exists mainly in the form of H_2CrO_4 ¹²⁻¹⁴. In view of the observed order of unity in both QDC and

ethylene glycol concentrations, ethylene glycol reacts with H_2CrO_4 in a rate-determining step to give a free radical derived from ethylene glycol and chromium(V) being generated. This intermediate chromium(V) reacts with the free radical of ethylene glycol in a fast step to give the product, glycollic aldehyde and the intermediate chromium(IV) species. Another molecule of ethylene glycol reacts with chromium(IV) in a further fast step to give a free radical derived from ethylene glycol and the intermediate species chromium(IV). In a further fast step two moles of chromium(IV) reacts with one mole of ethylene glycol to give the products chromium(III) and glycollic aldehyde. The initiation of polymerization of acrylonitrile indicated the presence of a free radical intermediate. A free radical mechanism has been proposed¹³ for the oxidation of 2-propanol by chromium(VI) in aqueous acetic acid medium. The oxidation of ethylene glycol by quinolinium dichromate occurs by the intervention of reactive chromium(V) and chromium(IV) species. The intervention of chromium(V) is evident from the induction experiment with iodide¹³. The induced oxidation of iodide yields two equivalent of iodine for each equivalent of the inductor oxidized. The induction factor for iodide oxidation is nearly two, which indicates the active oxidizing agent is pentavalent chromium. The intervention of chromium(IV) is evident from the progressive rate decrease in the presence of increasing amounts of added manganese(II) and the decrease reaches a limit of about one half of the rate found in the absence of manganese(II). Such results have also been obtained for chromium(VI) oxidation of 2-propanol in acetic acid¹³.

From Scheme 1, the rate law (5) may be obtained as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{QDC}]}{dt} = k [\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4] [\text{ethylene glycol}] \quad (2)$$

But, from first step of Scheme 1, one has

$$[\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4] = K [\text{QDC}] [\text{H}^+]^2$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{QDC}]}{dt} \\ &= k K [\text{QDC}] [\text{ethylene glycol}] [\text{H}^+]^2 \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

The total concentration of quinolinium dichromate, $[\text{QDC}]_t$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{QDC}]_t &= [\text{QDC}]_f + \text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4 \\ &= [\text{QDC}]_f + K [\text{QDC}] [\text{H}^+]^2 \\ &= [\text{QDC}]_f \{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$[\text{QDC}]_f = \frac{[\text{QDC}]_t}{\{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2\}} \quad (4)$$

where 't' and 'f' stands for total and free.

Substituting eq. (4) in eq. (3) and omitting the subscripts one gets,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{QDC}]}{dt} \\ &= \frac{k K [\text{QDC}] [\text{ethylene glycol}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} k_{\text{obs}} &= \frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{QDC}]} \\ &= \frac{k K [\text{ethylene glycol}] [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K [\text{H}^+]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The rate law (5) explains all the experimentally observed orders and it is rearranged to eq. (6), which is suitable for verification

$$\frac{[\text{ethylene glycol}]}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k K [\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (6)$$

According to eq. (6) the plot of L.H.S. versus $1/[\text{H}^+]^2$ should be linear and is found to be so (Fig. 4). The slope and intercept of such plot lead to the values of K and k as

Fig. 4. Verification of rate law (5) in the form of (6) (Conditions as in Table 1).

(0.83 ± 0.01) $\text{dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2}$ and ($1.18 \times 10^{-2} \pm 0.02$) $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ in respectively. The value of K obtained is in reasonable agreement with literature¹². Using these values, k_{obs} under different experimental conditions were calculated and compared with experimental data. Experimental and calculated values agree reasonably well (Table 1).

$$(i) \text{ Intercept} = \frac{1}{k} = 84.79$$

$$k = 1.18 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$$

$$(ii) \text{ Slope} = \frac{1}{kK_1}$$

$$K_1 = \frac{1}{101.21 \times 0.0118} = 0.83 \text{ dm}^6 \text{mol}^{-2}$$

The effect of ionic strength is difficult to interpret in view of the various ions involved in the reaction and high ionic strength used. The effect of solvent on the reaction rate has been described in detail in the literature¹⁵. An increase in the content of acetic acid in the reaction medium leads to an increase in the reaction rate. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/D$ was linear with positive slope, which is contrary to the expected. Perhaps the effect is countered substantially by the formation of active reaction species to a greater extent in low dielectric constant media leading to the net increase in the rate. The mechanism is also supported by moderate values of thermodynamic parameters. The value of ΔS^\ddagger within the range of radical reactions has been ascribed to the nature of electron unpairing processes and to the loss of degree of freedom formerly available to the reactions.

The main products of reaction were found to be chromium(III), glycollic aldehyde. A mechanism in terms of active species of oxidant and reductant is proposed and the rate law is derived and verified.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in water, which had been twice distilled in an all-glass unit in the presence of potassium permanganate. Reagent grade chemicals were used. Quinolinium dichromate (QDC) was prepared by known method⁴⁻⁶ as follows: A known quantity of quinoline was slowly added to a cooled solution of chromium trioxide in water with stirring. After 30 min, the solution was diluted with acetone and cooled to -20°C for 15-18

h. The orange solid, which separates out was filtered, washed with acetone, dried in vacuum and then recrystallised from water. It was characterized by IR spectroscopy and melting point (Found : 159 °C, Reported : 160–161 °C) determination. The stock solution of QDC was prepared by dissolving in water and concentration was ascertained iodometrically⁶. A stock solution of ethylene glycol was prepared by dissolving ethylene glycol (Sisco Chem) in water. The chromium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving chromium(III) potassium sulphate (BDH, AR), Cr₂(SO₄)₃·K₂SO₄·24H₂O in water. Perchloric acid (70%, E. Merck) was the source of H⁺ utilized to vary the acid concentration in the reaction media. The ionic strength was maintained constant with sodium perchlorate (AR).

Kinetics were followed at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C and I = 1.10 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostatted reactant solutions of quinolinium dichromate and ethylene glycol, which also contained the required quantity of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate. The kinetics were followed under pseudo-first order conditions with [ethylene glycol] > [QDC] at a constant ionic strength of 1.10 mol dm⁻³ by measuring the absorbance of QDC in the reaction mixture at 440 nm in a 1 cm cell placed in the thermostatted cell compartment of Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Application of Beer's law under the reaction condition had been verified between 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ and 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ of QDC at 440 nm and extinction coefficient ε was found to be 390 ± 10 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The kinetic runs were followed more than 90% completion of the reaction and good first order kinetics was observed. The pseudo-first order rate constant *k*_{obs} was calculated from plots of log (absorbance) versus time (Fig. 1). The pseudo-first order plots, almost in all cases, were linear over 80% completion of the reaction (Fig. 1). The *k*_{obs} values were reproducible within ±5% and are the average of at least three independent kinetics runs (Table 1).

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